

RESEARCH DATA ALLIANCE

doi. [10.15497/RDA00100](https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00100)

RDA for UN Sustainable Development Goal 17

Celebrating A Decade of Data
RDA community cross-fertilisation workshop

Version: September 2023

ABOUT THE WORKSHOP

The community cross-fertilisation workshop, 'RDA for UN Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 17: Capacity building, data sharing, infrastructure and development', brought chairs and members of RDA community groups together, with members of the wider research data community, to share and discuss challenges, solutions and initiatives associated with contributing to SDG17. The key findings of the workshop summarised herein will be used to direct the future strategy of the RDA community. Read more about the [community cross-fertilisation workshop series](#) in commemoration of the [RDA's 10th Anniversary](#).

CHALLENGES TO BE ADDRESSED RELATING TO UN SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOAL 17: CAPACITY BUILDING, DATA SHARING, INFRASTRUCTURE AND DEVELOPMENT

Data for the SDGs

- All SDGs are broad in scope, ambition and are interrelated which makes their achievement challenging. In particular, SDG 17, '[Revitalise the global partnership for sustainable development](#)', requires wide cooperation at the organisational, disciplinary, and geo-political level.
- Need for rapid access to high-quality, real-time, trusted and disaggregated data to support implementation and monitoring of UN SDGs, also during crisis situations. Data silos and lack of data standardisation hinders data sharing and reuse.
- Lack of clarity of data collection protocols, SDG-related data management workflows, and data authentication and authorisation policies (e.g., data use, consent and access agreements).
- The difference between 'data' and 'evidence' is ill-defined. The same data is collected repeatedly during crisis situations which can be problematic, particularly with regard to the collection of sensitive data from human subjects. There is a need to protect the rights of vulnerable population sub-groups.

International Policy

- Need for data-driven, decision-making and evidence-based policies to effectively address development challenges.
- Need for development of accountable governance frameworks to enable lawful and ethical cross-border data collection, sharing and reuse to enable innovation and societal benefit.
- Policies to incentivise public-private partnerships, open science and knowledge sharing across borders, directing research and investment toward achieving the UN SDGs

Social and cultural

- Lack of human resources, education, training, and knowledge brokering, makes it difficult to drive a culture change towards Open Science and contribute toward the UN SDGs.
- Maintaining sustainability of work towards SDGs requires continuous awareness raising campaigns which is laborious and time consuming.
- Need more education and advocacy around SDGs to be able to identify relevant RDA community groups and engage them in activities to contribute towards the goals.

PARTICIPATING GROUP & WORKSHOP LEAD*

[RDA for the Sustainable Development Goals IG](#)

Workshop lead: [Anthony Luehne](#)

[See community group card](#)

[Data for Development IG](#)

Workshop lead: [Noman Mukasa](#)

[See community group card](#)

[RDA / CODATA Data Systems, Tools, and Services for Crisis Situations WG](#)

Workshop lead: [Stefanie Kethers](#)

[See community group card](#)

[Artificial Intelligence and Data Visitation \(AIDV\) WG](#)

Workshop lead: [Natalie Meyers](#)

[See community group card](#)

*The workshop lead collected challenges, solutions and initiatives in preparation for the workshop and explained them during the workshop on behalf of their group.

CHALLENGES CONT.

Regional

- Lack of international policies, partnerships, infrastructure development, and resources to enable open sharing and reuse of data to achieve and sustain SDGs.
- Need to encourage resource and knowledge flow between the Global North and South.
- Lack of education infrastructure and digitalisation in the Global South. Gaps in capacity building and technological limitations, such as access to the internet, data, and Artificial Intelligence (AI), hinder development of research in some countries. E.g. African universities produce <1% of scientific articles.

ACTIONS FOR THE RDA COMMUNITY

Raise awareness and increase engagement of RDA groups in contributing towards the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

- Organise events and activities for groups working towards one or more SDGs to identify common interests and collaborations.
- This could be supported via the RDA web platform and/or virtual [Whova](#) platform during RDA Plenary meetings.
- Encourage emergent leaders within the RDA to become 'ambassadors' for specific SDGs, encouraging community members to contribute to relevant SDG-related groups, tasks, and activities.

Identify and map groups that are directly or indirectly contributing to one or more SDGs.

- Use Working and Interest Group Case Statements and Charters to identify and map groups to SDGs.
- Provide digital badges on RDA group web pages which showcase which SDGs a group contributes to.
- Ask Plenary session organisers to specify how their session contributes to one or more SDGs.
- Contribute to [OntoSDG \(Knowledge Management Framework for UN SDGs\)](#), which provides a semantic ontology for mapping RDA work (groups, outputs, etc.) to SDGs.

Facilitate global dissemination and outreach to showcase the RDA's contribution to the SDGs.

- Plan for engagement of the RDA with the [United Nations](#) and other [inter] governmental organisations.
- Publish a special collection in the [Data Science Journal](#) on 'The Role of Open Science in the Achievement of the UN SDGs'.
- Continue to focus on Open Science, and work related to the [Global Open Research Commons \(GORC\)](#) and [European Open Science Cloud \(EOSC\)](#).

Continue to cultivate regional partnerships within the Global South

- Continue to encourage, integrate and include RDA members from the Global South in RDA work, e.g., ensuring geographical diversity of group co-chairs, and organising timezone friendly events.
- Identify and promote RDA groups, and outputs and recommendations that have a focus on the Global South.
- Organise an event series to identify the needs of specific regions/countries in the Global South, and in turn, identify RDA groups and activities that might meet those needs.
- Establish an [RDA regional partnership](#) with Africa.

INITIATIVES & RESOURCES OF INTEREST

- [A Framework for Evaluating and Disclosing the ESG Related Impacts of AI with the SDGs](#) - Publication
- [African Association for Universities \(AAU\)](#)
- [African Open Science Platform \(AOSP\)](#)
- [AI for Social Good: Unlocking the Opportunity for Positive Impact](#) - Publication
- [AlgorithmWatch](#)
- [Artificial Intelligence and Data Visitation \(AIDW\) WG Zotero Library - Subcollection on SDGs](#)
- [Artificial Intelligence \(AI\) and Sustainable Development Goals \(SDGs\): Exploring the Impact of AI on Politics and Society](#) - Publication
- [CARE principles for Indigenous Data Governance: Collective benefit, Authority to control, Responsibility and Ethics.](#)
- [CODATA International Data Policy Committee \(IDPC\)](#)
- [Department of Economic and Social Affairs \(DESA\)](#)
- [East Africa Scientific Research Network \(EASRN\)](#)
- [Economic and Social Commission for Asia and the Pacific \(ESCAP\)](#)
- [European Digital Rights \(EDRi\)](#)
- [Global Open Science Cloud \(GOSC\)](#)
- [GSMA](#)
- [Harvard Humanitarian Initiative](#)
- [Humanitarian Open StreetMap](#)
- [ICANN Regional At-Large Organisations](#) - E.g., [AFRALO](#) African Regional At-Large Organisation
- [Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers \(IEEE\)](#)
- [OntoSDG](#)
- [Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development \(OECD\)](#)
- [Productive Employment and Decent Work: The Impact of AI Adoption on Psychological Contracts, Job Engagement and Employee Trust](#) - Publication
- [Red Iberoamericana de Ciencia Participativa](#)
- [Regulating Artificial-Intelligence Applications to Achieve the Sustainable Development Goals](#) - Publication

INITIATIVES & RESOURCES OF INTEREST CONT.

- [Research Ideas and Outcomes](#) Journal which has [mapped all publications to SDGs](#) since 2015.
- [Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction 2015-2030](#)
- [The International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions \(IFLA\)](#)
- [The Role of Artificial Intelligence in Achieving the Sustainable Development Goals](#) - Publication
- [The Role of Artificial Intelligence in Building Responsible Open Science Frameworks](#)
- [The WorldFAIR Project](#) (development of interoperable standards)
- [TRUST Principles for digital repositories: Transparency, Responsibility, User Focus, Sustainability and Technology](#)
- [United Nations - Statistics Division Development Data and Outreach Branch](#)
- [UN Global Pulse](#)
- [UNESCO](#)
- [Wikimedians for Disaster Response](#)
- [World Health Organisation \(WHO\)](#)
- [World Wide Web Consortium \(W3C\)](#)

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For more information about the RDA community cross-fertilisation workshop series, please contact Community Development Manager, Connie Clare (connie.clare@rda-foundation.org)

To become a member of the RDA, register [here](#)